

PERCEPTIONS OF PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS ON CONTINUING PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT TOWARDS AN INTERVENTION PROGRAM

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Abstract: The purpose of this exploratory qualitative single case study was to describe the perceptions of five public secondary school teachers in East District of Malungon, Division of Sarangani. Qualitative research design using a single case study approach was employed to traverse and interpret the perceptions of Continuing Professional Development that leads to an intervention program. Five participants went through an in-depth interview to discover their perception using thematic analysis in analyzing the data. The data gathered were categorized into three themes: needs for Continuing Professional Development, perceived challenges on Continuing Professional Development, and the Impact of Continuing Professional Development. Teachers need to be updated and be equipped with the skills and knowledge to cope up with the fast-changing trends in education through acquiring CPD activities in the school context.

Keywords: educational management, perceptions, continuing professional development, teachers, intervention program, Philippine.

“Who dares to teach must never cease to learn.”

- John Cotton Dana

1. INTRODUCTION

Recent studies in continuing professional development with different focuses were conducted, and numerous mistaken assumptions arise about professional development, its purpose, and its functions. This study is relevant to teachers as this will give insights based on the different perceptions of teachers, in strengthening the quality of Continuing Professional Development that leads to an intervention program.

In education, CPD plays a considerable part; basically, it is seen that the quality of our educational system depends on the quality of our teachers. Proceeding with professional development experts recommend that coordinated, and appropriately planned CPD can incite successful changes in teachers' practice, redesigns at the institutional level, and vast

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improvements in student achievement. Moreover, CPD participation in many countries is viewed as an obligation: In Poland, the educational system demands teacher development in promotion, while in Spain and Italy, they are obliged to take an interest in a specific training every year. In any case, the effectiveness of CPD will be severely limited if participants are not interested (Campbell, M. P. & Elliot, R., 2015; Belay, S., 2016; Srinivasacharlu, A., 2019).

CPD is misleadingly defined in a simple description of a massively complex intellectual and emotional endeavor focused on raising standards of teaching, learning, and achievement in an educational setting, every one of which represents its own set of challenges. The research aims to identify the perception of secondary school teachers on continuing professional development that would serve as a basis for a proposed intervention program.

Statement of the Problem

Studying the perceptions of public secondary school teachers on Continuing Professional Development was necessary. It would deepen the knowledge and understanding of the importance and effect of it on individuals, learners, and the community. Teachers should widen and enhance their learning to help them do better in their profession.

Sarangani Province is one of the components of The SOCSKSARGEN region located in South Central Mindanao. Malungon is one of the seven municipalities that consists Sarangani Province; it borders General Santos City and Davao Del Sur and is composed of 31 barangays. East Malungon District includes schools that are in barangay Tamban, Lutay, and Lower Mainit. The district is composed of one National High School, seven Integrated Schools, fifteen Elementary Schools, and one IP school. There are 69 teachers in secondary and 171 teachers in elementary.

The fast-changing pace of technology now challenged teachers; hence, they needed to upgrade themselves in education. This study aims to know the perception of public secondary school teachers in the East Malungon District on continuing professional development. It would help teachers interpret their perception of continuing professional development in the research context and what they need to improve to be efficient in their chosen field. Hence the result of the study would serve as the basis for a proposed intervention program.

Purpose Statement

This exploratory qualitative single case study analyzed the perceptions of secondary school teachers in East Malungon District through their continuing professional development experiences that would be a basis for an intervention program. Continuous professional development should be self-directed, planned, and considered part of professional life. Subsequently, the state also ensures the profession's promotion and upgrading practice stipulated in Implementing Rules and Regulations (IRR) of Republic Act No. 10912 (PRC Resolution No. 2019-1146, 2019; Porter, B. D. & Freeman, M. K., 2020; Burton, L., 2021).

Results of this case study of teachers of East Malungon District would explore and interpret the perceptions and experiences of teachers in terms of difficulty, thwarting factors, contribution, and preferences concerning continuing professional development that would be a basis to an intervention program.

This study would benefit learners, teachers, administration, the school, and the community. It is essential to unveil the teacher's perception of continuing professional development to evaluate its effect on their work and profession, leading to an intervention program. It could also serve as a basis for future alternative intervention programs to enhance the skills and knowledge of teachers to be more effective and efficient.

Research Questions

This exploratory qualitative single case study was designed to explore and interpret the perceptions of five public secondary school teachers in East Malungon, Malungon Sarangani Province.

Specifically, the study sought to answer these grand tour questions:

1. How do participants perceive Continuing Professional Development?
2. What intervention program could be proposed based on the finding of the study?

Theoretical Lens

This study was based on the theory of connectivism by Downes (2007), as cited by AlDahdouh, et. al. (2015) states, "thesis that knowledge is distributed across a network of connections, and therefore that learning consists of the ability to construct and traverse those networks. Connectivism was categorized as a mirror of our society that was fast-changing. Society becomes more complex, linked socially, globally, and facilitated by increasing improvements in technology—the composition of a difficult confusion of ideas networked to form exact information sets. Different opinions are ways of knowing. It was a collaboration of existing ideas, and individuals did not have control. The fundamental ability was to see networks of information sources and sustain that connection to enable continuous learning. Decisions were maintained by swiftly changing fundamentals as new information was rapidly included to create a new set of thinking. Knowledge was disseminated across linkages of connections to people and information, thus learning to be made up the ability to build and pass through those networks.

Supported by Radical Constructivism theory by Ernst Von Glasersfeld (1995), as cited by Sharkey and Gash (2020), it underlines the unavailability of reality. It proposes his view that the function of cognition was adaptive. There was no discerning method of knowing anything outside the area of our experience, and through it, we construct our world. Since knowledge was certifiably not an adaptable item, learning was, for the most part, related to the action of the development of particular importance. Sociocultural of Vygotsky (1978), as cited by Razak, et. al. (2015), supports by pointing out the significant role of social interaction in the development of cognition. Vygotsky strongly believed that community plays an essential role in the "making meaning" process. The individual could design their future or develop something specified to be guided. Social constructivism gave grounding in that all knowledge improves due to social interaction and language use. For that reason, it was a collective experience; therefore, it means that skills cannot be mastered by individuals but requires the guidance of an expert or skilled peer.

2. METHODOLOGY

Qualitative research has been found to conquer the limitations of quantitative research. Regardless of the popularity and advantages of the quantitative approach, it did not apply to a wide range of studies because not all studies or analyses could yield numerical data. A qualitative approach may utilize to conduct studies unrelated to numbers or mathematical measures. It discovers its wide application in many studies, including sociology, educational and academic analysis, and numerous fields. Qualitative research focuses on the translation of the view of individuals from a social viewpoint utilizing different qualitative collections of data, including interviews, social queries, surveys, or reviews.

Moreover, the results of qualitative research would, in general, be descriptive. Conducting an in-depth interview on any social or educational phenomena would depend on participants' views. Proper integration of qualitative research is fundamental; it helps build essential connections between the researcher and people, encouraging better comprehension of reality and interpreting the outcome as a qualitative methodology (Glesne, C., 2016; Kozleski, E. B., 2017; Aspers, P. & Corte, U., 2019).

In this research, an exploratory qualitative single case study was employed. The case study is suitable when examining complex phenomena in naturalistic settings. It typically includes a few cases, which allows the issues to study in-depth. This exploratory approach fundamentally pointed to our understanding of continuing professional development according to the participants' perceptions. The case study provides the "working hypotheses" from which different arrangement cases (transferability) might be conceivable and depend upon the similarities between the source case and the target cases instead of the generalization findings (Allen, M., 2017; Barrow, D. M., 2017; BERA, 2018).

Furthermore, this would also be the most suitable research methodology, because the concern of the study was to recognize how people make sense of their lives. The researcher needs to know the participants' perceptions about continuing professional development. The researchers emphasize the participants' perception about continuing professional development. The researcher would make an honest effort to precisely catch the participants' perceptions as expected. It is noted that she could gain insights from cases over and done with thorough discussions through a case study. The researcher was interested in knowing the perception of the secondary public-school teachers in a particular district and how they can interpret and discover its importance.

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The researcher conducted a semi-structured interview with the selected teachers in East Malungon District to gather data. Inside and out investigation of participants' perception was encouraged and, if feasible, the researcher would utilize audio recordings of the meeting to secure its validity and get the essential information simultaneously to forestall biases. Furthermore, the thematic analysis was used to interpret the data gathered.

Research Site and Purposeful Sampling

The study was conducted at the selected integrated schools and one National High School in East Malungon District, Malungon, Sarangani Province.

The participants are public secondary school teachers, Teacher 1 in position, two males and three females, 5 to 10 years in service, and age ranges from 25-35 years old. They were selected through purposive random sampling. The researcher selects participants using the indicated criterion.

Participants were determined through purposive sampling. The researcher selects the population members to participate in the study based on his judgment. This selection was purposeful and required. It does not focus on the quantity of data or sources but whether it should be sufficiently rich to bring refinement and clarity to understand an experience. This sampling was appropriate for qualitative studies, where the researcher was interested in the participants who had the best information concerning the study (Creswell, J. W., 2015; Eakin, J. M., 2016; Allen, M., 2017).

Researcher's Role and Potential Ethical Issues

Learners learn from their teachers, so it is essential to be equipped with the skills and knowledge to teach effectively. Updating Continuing Professional Development is one of the challenges that the teachers find challenging to keep on track. It is often offered by external providers, limited opportunities, and financial stability may also be at stake.

The researcher is assigned within the district, but still, proper coordination was done in gaining access to participants before the conduct of the study. Authorization and consent letter was distributed to the participants to achieve their approval to be the research informants. A copy of consent was given to all the participants at the time of the interview. The interview was conducted at the most ideal and suitable time for the participants. Participants were allowed to peruse and clarify the data from the consent, including the objectives and procedure. The researcher made it clear that the participants could decline participation at any time of the study to clarify that the participation is voluntary. The researcher should ask that each participant allows audio recording of the interview for the analysis to turn out to be more tenable. This strategy would lessen the risk that the conclusions would reflect the systematic biases. The researcher guaranteed that all the data given by the participants was dealt confidential and private.

The researcher kept up with the obscurity of the participants by substituting their names with letters and numbers. In this manner, it is valuable in defending them to public opinions and secures participants' personalities. These guaranteed participants' statements were confidential, giving them a verbal oath of confidentiality and signing a paper expressing that using these assertions was only used for the purpose of the study.

Honesty assumes an indispensable part in this study. The researcher revealed and translated data appropriately to acquire the participants' trust—a way of building rapport and developing the participants' confidence. In analyzing data, try not to take sides with the participants and report positive and negative data. Stay away from imprudent blunders and carelessness and consistently keep a record and duplicate everything about the study to guarantee reliable data.

Like the audio recording, the data gathered was then carefully kept yet erased towards the end of the study to abide by the Data Privacy Act in research studies. Thematic analysis was used in data analysis using the collected data from the survey.

Data Gathering Strategies

The researcher used an arising qualitative approach to inquiry, the natural setting of data collection that was sensitive to participants of the study and places and data analysis that were both inductive and deductive and set up themes, which means breaking down the articles into clear or general ideas. The interview was conducted depending on the availability and preference of the participants. The interview guide question was based on the modified in-depth interview guide of Lofland and Lofland (1995), as cited by Showkat and Parveen (2017).

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An in-depth interview would be composed of five secondary teachers from East Malungon District. Participants were determined through purposive sampling. The researcher selected the population members to participate in the study based on his judgment. This selection was purposeful and required. It sought to bring refinement and clarity by focusing on the quantity of data or from sources through participants' perceptions. Researchers may include 2 to 25 participants experiencing the same phenomenon in in-depth interviews. It is significant to choose rich cases for an in-depth study. Information-rich cases could be sought to learn boundless deals about the issues of central importance on the purpose of the research (Creswell, J. W., 2015; Alase, A., 2017; Bolt, C. A., 2017).

Preceding the actual interview, preliminary gathering with the participants would take place and make a short conversation to get their trust and certainty to set up camaraderie. It was an incredible possibility for clarifying the purpose and the significance of their function in the outcome and result of the research study, tended to their inquiries and concerns, reviewed some moral ethics, and finished the consent form. Through this, they would have the opportunity to consider their encounters before the actual interview happens.

The researcher sought endorsement from experts in qualitative studies during the research questions validation. Research instruments used, mainly the interview guide questions, were validated and checked. Validators affirmed their approval through their signatures in the Validation Form attached to Appendix G. The researcher contemplated on suggestions and recommendations provided. It is to ensure that the study would be given its appropriate uprightness to capture the perceptions of the teacher.

The researcher adhered to the ethical procedures required by Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges. Questions contained within the interview guide navigated to understand and interpret the perceptions of secondary public-school teachers on continuing professional development.

Data Analysis Approach

Qualitative data analysis needs to be conducted with vigor and care. It requires that the researcher dwell with or become immersed in the data. Data analysis was done to preserve the uniqueness of each participant's description and then read and re-read the verbatim transcription. It was seen as the "precise methodology to distinguish relevant features and relationships" and changing the information through understanding (Ngulube, P., 2015; Sutton, J. & Austin, Z., 2015; Roulston, K., 2017).

Bracketing and phenomenological reduction, delineating units of meaning, clustering of units of meaning to form themes, summarising each interview and validating it and, where necessary modifying it and extracting general and unique articles from all the interviews. Making a composite summary were the five stages of explicit that would be used in the study. Bracketing and phenomenological reduction refer to the bracketing of the personal views or presumptions of the researcher. They delineate units of meaning, thus requiring the researcher to make a considerable amount of judgment calls while deliberately bracketing his assumptions to avoid incorrect subjective conclusions. Clustering units of meaning to form themes means grouping the units, categorizing the relevant subject matter, and summarising each interview through validation and modification that integrates all gathered from the data to give a whole perspective. Thus, the researcher made a composite summary by reflecting on the themes' context (Creswell, J. W., 2015; Alase, A., 2017; Howitt, D., 2017; Isabirye, A. K. & Makoe, M., 2018; Clearfield, T., 2019; Dörfler, V. & Stierand, M., 2020).

Trustworthiness in qualitative studies uses legitimacy and unwavering quality methods to test the quality of instruments that measure the marvels under the research and qualify findings as absolutely speaking the information in unmistakable and critical manners. The research design project's trustworthiness approaches were credibility, dependability, conformability, transferability, and authenticity (Creswell, J. W., 2015; Amankwaa, L., 2016; Ahmed, S. W., & Siddiqui, D., 2020).

Credibility guarantees that the participants agree to have and do note-taking. The data gathered will be agreeably handled and concurred by the researcher and the participants to make the collected data more credible. The data proven to be confirmed and validated will allow at least two individuals to appear reasonably strong. Credibility implies the truth of the member's information and the analyst's understanding and portrayal. Credibility was upgraded by the researcher depicting their experiences and checking the research findings with the participants (Connelly, L., 2016; Glesne, C., 2016; Allen, M., 2017).

Transferability adjusts and notifies the part, discusses in detail the research context, derivation, and assumptions that are the research's focal point, and presents all data as clear as could be expected. It guarantees that the accumulated data are rich with descriptions, so any individual who wants to transfer the results and outcome to different circumstances is then responsible for judging how sensible the transfer is. Transferability alludes to whether the results obtained from the analysis can be applied to other settings and contexts. It goes about as a check for the external validity of the findings. Analysts gave a detailed description of the locations and context of the research. It is done to provide the readers with enough information to pass judgment on the relevance of the findings to different settings with their very own encounters (Connolly, L., 2016; Amankwaa, L., 2016; Allen, M., 2017).

Confirmability reminds the researcher to put to the side closely-held convictions, assumptions, and judgments to make preparations against destroying data. The utilization of audio-taped meetings, note-taking, and journals throughout the study guarantees the confirmability in leading the investigation that contributes to getting the genuine picture of the participants' individual experiences. It keeps away from personal inclination, and the bracketing approach would be utilized as a methodology component. It follows triangulation, and peer consensus should be applied to guarantee that the study's findings would be free from individual biases and inclinations. Confirmability likewise shows a way to demonstrate quality. The researcher may analyze the methodology utilized in the research focus to build up conformability. Triangulation techniques in data, researcher and context, can also be valuable tools of confirmability (Bengtsson, M., 2016; Trochim, W., Donnelly, J. & Arora, K., 2016; Polit, D. F. & Beck, C. T., 2017).

Ethical Considerations

Before beginning the study, permission was sought from principal in-charge to carry out the survey in the district. Hence, a letter outlining the research proposal requesting written consent to conduct the research was sent to the district principal in-charge. It is imperative to obtain the host's permission and provide them with necessary information on the nature and purpose of the study (Ngulube, P., 2015; Allen, M., 2017; Bartleton, L., 2018).

The study was conducted within the perimeter of ethical standards to make confident, informed consent from all participants. The purpose of the study was laid out at the Informed Consent Form. It gave the participants clarification of the nature and reason of the study. Accordingly, the confidentiality of all the participants was taken care of; anonymity was ensured to all participants by guaranteeing that no names would be revealed throughout the investigation. Furthermore, participants' responses were recorded using numbers and letters to substitute their words (Igwenagu, C., 2016; Allen, M., 2017; BERA, 2018).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The researcher conducted an in-depth interview among the five participants teaching in East Malungon District to accumulate the needed data to describe their perceptions on continuing professional development.

The researcher transcribed the audio recordings, read the transcription thoroughly, classified the data by importance, and presented the themes through the research questions in the study; the researcher made a thematic analysis, to create emergent themes.

Presented the main findings that describe the participants' responses relating to the question: How do participants perceive Continuing Professional Development are also presented. The main themes generated are the Needs for Continuing Professional Development, Perceived Challenges on Continuing Professional Development, and the Impact of Continuing Professional Development.

The Needs for Continuing Professional Development theme were composed of Continuous Learning, Professional Standard, Professional License Renewal, Capacitate, Relevant to Work, In-service Training, Knowledge Application, and the Organizational CPD. The Encountered Challenges belongs to the theme Perceived Challenges on Continuing Professional Development. Additional Learning, Task Fulfillment, Curriculum Implementation, Engage Learners, School Achievement, Student Applied Learning, Students Performance, Teachers Competence, Teachers Assessment, and the Curriculum Instruction were the emergent theme that arose in the Impact of Continuing Professional Development.

Table 1: Main Theme: Needs for Continuing Professional Development

Cluster Themes	Emergent Themes
A. Understanding of Continuing Professional Development 1. Continue to learn 2. Learning and growth management 3. Developing professional skills 4. Ongoing developmental process 5. Continuous training	1. Continuous Learning
B. Upgrade Continuing Professional Development 6. CPD enforcement 7. Improve professional skills 8. Meet the standards 9. Comply practice	2. Professional Standard
C. Exigencies arise that motivates 10. PRC renewal 11. Certificates with points 12. Update professional skills	3. Professional License Renewal
D. Need to strengthened 13. Professional development 14. Capacitate employees 15. Enhance skills 16. Updated of education trends 17. Appropriate to teachers need	4. Capacitate
E. Effective CPD strategy that inspires and engage 18. Applicable 19. Hands-on training and seminars 20. Well-formulated 21. Aligned and accurate for school works	5. Relevant to Work
F. Undertaken Professional Development opportunities 22. Training and seminars initiated by the Department 23. School Learning Action Cell 24. Curriculum aspect	6. In-service Training
G. Improve teaching and learning process 25. Lesson preparation and delivery 26. Track and document progress through self-assessment 27. Sharing notions to colleagues 28. Right application in works	7. Knowledge Application
H. Availing department CPD activities to maximize utilization 29. School-sponsored 30. Attending department seminars and training 31. Offer free or affordable seminars and training	8. Organizational CPD

The public secondary school teachers' perception revealed a need for continuing professional development. As curriculum implementation evolves, teachers need to cope with the education trends. Teachers should continue to learn for them to teach efficiently and effectively.

Continuous Learning

The participants understand continuing professional development as a process of continuous learning that enables them to function well in their profession. Teachers should continue learning to cope with the fast and changing trends in education. These guarantees the improvement and updating of abilities, including obtaining new skills and knowledge, as indicated as necessities in the education curriculum, as regards the teachers' competency to the progressions of the educational system.

"Since we are a professional, there is a need to continue to learn, and they say that learning is continuous." (P1) (3-4)

"... professional management of one's learning and growth. That helps expand the knowledge and skills required in their respective work field." (P2) (119-121)

"... process of developing professional skills of the field you're into. I did say it for if you're engaged in these activities, you'll acquire new knowledge, new skills that would be of great help to grow more on your chosen field of endeavor." (P3) (220-223)

"...on-going, planned learning and developmental process. I can say that it is a process because it enables employees to expand and fulfill their potential." (P4) (304-307)

"... continuous training of teachers to be expert in the field of teaching." (P5) (394-395)

Teachers' professional development plays an essential role in changing teaching methods and assisting teachers in moving beyond understanding the surface features of a new idea or innovation to a deeper understanding of a topic. A good definition of continuous learning is our drive to remain lifelong learners. As mature students, the significant achievement

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is to turn out to be all the more intrinsically motivated. Moreover, teachers learn best through professional development that tends to their necessities. Teacher professional development should hence be regarded as a continuous process. Thus, it implied that learning is a lifelong process. If teachers cannot cope with the global changes, particularly those that come with technology, they will not fit in this period (Selwyn, N., 2016; Livingston, K., 2017; Bernadine, G. G. K., 2019; Zorn, F., 2020).

CPD embraces various approaches and teaching and learning styles in different settings the broader concept of learning. Activities involved are classroom management, budgeting, purchasing, resourcefulness, and lesson planning. Teachers should be engaged to additionally develop expertise in subject matter content, technologies, and other fundamental components that lead to high standards and quality in teaching. Learning new knowledge and skills keeps individuals motivated, valued, and flexible to change; and is generally associated with professional identities, roles, and goals. (Witte, T. & Jansen, E., 2016; Harackiewicz, J. M., Smith, J. L. & Priniski, S. J., 2018; Baral, D. P., 2021).

Professional Standards

Professional standards were set to have guidance on the direction of the teachers to take. The standards gave the framework to a teacher's profession and explained progress. Maintaining professional standards was the primary reason to upgrade the continuing professional development.

"... to force and re-enforce the bill that was amended by one of the senators because maybe in their study some of the professionals are not updated to renew." (P1) (15-17)

"... for us to improve professional skills and can move towards higher standards as required by the new trend being implemented in our curriculum today." (P2) (129-131)

"We need to upgrade the CPD for teachers for us to improve professional skills and can move towards higher standards and professional skills." (P4) (312-314)

"... to comply in practice and appropriate to the challenges brought by new trends." (P5) (398-400)

Teachers are the compass that directs practice through policymakers, professionals, and supporting organizations. They do not endorse explicit actions, encouraging those engaged with educational leadership and its improvement to adjust their application to the best conditions and contexts. As stipulated in DepEd Order No. 42, known as National Adoption and Implementation of the Professional Standards for Teachers (NAIPST), quality learning depends on quality teaching. Consequently, upgrading teachers' quality was significant for long-term and sustainable nation-building. Its most basic translation is tied to being in service to the public. It is about accomplishing great work in your obligation (National Policy Board for Educational Administration, 2015; Usman, Y. D., 2016; Llego, M. A., 2017; Evers, J., 2018).

Trends in education changed significantly during the most recent few decades. The assumptions of teachers and students have been changing as time passes by. Teachers are forced and expected to develop their teaching skills to cope with the fast-changing literary standards. The current time of innovation requests high professional skills of services from teachers to satisfy learners, parents, and the school. Thus, teachers are reflective and inquire professionals who contemplate their educational assumptions, qualities, and practice regarding a changing contemporary and academic world. They understand their role and responsibilities in teaching and as a professional. Teachers are both subject professionals in teaching and learning. They are focused on keeping up and building up their expertise to guarantee the best results for their students (Education and Training Foundation, 2015; Benade, L., 2015; Earl, K. & Ussher, B., 2015; Draz, M. U. & Ahmad, F., 2017).

Professional License Renewal

The difficulty motivating a teacher to take continuing professional development activity was for professional license renewal. It is why teachers took CPD activities to comply with the requirements set. Recently, the Department of Education issued a memorandum that teachers should have their license renewed and not expire primarily when they practice their profession.

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“Number 1 is PRC renewal ... “ (P1) (23)

“... the certificates with corresponding points that is a requirement in license renewal.” (P2) (135-136)

“.... PRC’s renewal and be not left behind in new techniques and strategies in teaching.” (P3) (231-232)

“The PRC renewal and updating professional skills.” (P4) (317)

License holders are responsible for fulfilling requirements for license renewal as set by the licensure regulations for school personnel. Professionals shall comply with the mandatory units every three years. Hence, it requires both educational and experiential components that reflect the understanding and extent of the knowledge contained in the education field (The Summit Express, 2017; Department of Teacher Education and Licensure, 2018; PRC Resolution No. 2019-1146, 2019; Professional Massachusetts License and License Renewal, 2021).

Section 2 is the Declaration of Policy which stated the Implementing Rules and Regulation of Republic Act 10912, also known as the Continuing Professional Development Act of 2016. These declare that the state stipulated the policy to promote and upgrade the practice of 43 professions in the country by acquiring learning activities that would advance knowledge, abilities, and specialized competencies. The competence of the professionals ensures that it is parallel and follows international standards. Therefore, it guarantees the contribution of professionals to uplift the general welfare, economic growth, and the development of the country (Llego, M. A., 2017; Yap, J. M. & Canceran, G. G., 2017; PRC Resolution No. 2019-1146, 2019).

Capacitate

Capacitate was the emergent theme that arises in need to strengthen Continuing Professional Development. Teachers are expected to fulfill their tasks responsibly. Teachers justify this by continuously upgrading skills and knowledge that can be applied in the teaching field and adapting to the changes.

“... strengthened for professional development for the benefit of the learners, workplace, self...” (P1) (41-42)

“... strengthened to capacitate the employees and to be globally competitive in terms of service.” (P2) (145-146)

“... it enables individuals to enhance their skills in whatever field he is in.” (P3) (241-242)

“... to make sure that the teachers are capable and updated of the education trends.” (P4) (326-327)

“... to be more appropriate to teachers need.” (P5) (415-416)

CPD means creating career development programs for lifelong learners that intend to assist various professionals in gaining applicable skills and knowledge to advance their work performance. Professionals in these areas should keep on capacitating themselves and adapt to rapid changes. There is a need and a place for teachers' Continuing Professional Development specifically for the development and improvement of our educational establishments.

Most teachers would recognize the requirement for continued technology training, homeroom practice, evaluation, and updates on educational policy. Positively excellent and effective teacher upgrades can influence teachers' abilities and perspectives in the classroom, which is an essential advantage to increase learners' education. It allows the learner to proactively nurture their professional capabilities through certified learning or independent learning method (Macheng, P., 2016; Dlamini, R. & Mbatha, K., 2018; Bartleton, L., 2018; Burton, L., 2021).

Relevant to Work

The change is most likely faster than it's consistently been - and this is a component of the new normal that we live and work. Teachers should be mindful of updating knowledge and skills applicable in the education system. An effective strategy that inspires and motivates teachers to take up continuing professional development activities should be relevant to their work. Teachers are passionate about applying their knowledge and skills gained like their work.

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“Effective teaching strategies and methods that are applicable in my field.” (P1) (48-49)

“Hands-on training and seminars with technical assistance are the best CPD practices for me, because guidance for improvement can possibly get here and it may be in a high range of possibilities; thus improvement and professional development could be met.” (P2) (153-156)

“Attending CPD credited seminars is one of the strategies that inspires me because of the well-formulated guides and teaching strategies can be learned and applied.” (P4) (330-332)

“... alignment and accuracy of my works in school.” (P5) (420-421)

Continuing professional development is adaptable, often collective, and contextually applicable to individual professional practice. The program guarantees the abilities of the professional are updated with the current standards; it further develops abilities expected to convey professional service and propel the collection of knowledge and innovation within the profession. It is an all-learning activity attempted all through life to further develop knowledge, abilities, and capabilities within personal, social, and employment perspectives. It concludes that it is an ongoing cycle that prompts further developed work fulfillment, professional goals, and intimate knowledge and capability improvement. They keep up with the latest advancements (Macheng, P., 2016; Queensland College of Teachers, 2017; U.S. Department of Education, 2017; Manley, K., Martin, A., Jackson, C., & Wright, T., 2018; Banegas, D. L. & Glatigny, R., 2021).

Professional development comprises all-natural learning encounters and those cognizant and planned activities that anticipate having an indirect or indirect benefit to the individual, group, or school, contributing to the classroom's education quality. It is the practice by which, alone and with others, teachers review, re-establish, and increase their responsibility as an agent of change to the moral purpose of teaching. They secure and critically develop knowledge, abilities, and emotional intelligence. It is necessarily good for professional thinking, planning, and practice with learners and colleagues all through each period of their teaching lives (Usman, Y. D., 2016; Livingston, K., 2017; Melesse S. & Gulie, K., 2019).

In-service Training

Teachers usually undertake professional development opportunities come from the department. In-service training is the activities held by the department to capacitate teachers through additional schooling or preparation to invigorate or upgrade their knowledge, skills, and practices throughout their career. These may add to the advancement of more grounded education and pedagogical strategies. Continuing professional development activities may be derived from school, district, region, or central office programs.

“... LAC session, In-Service Training, Division Seminar and Webinar.” (P1) (53-54)

“Attending training and seminars on teaching strategies and techniques, complying performance task assessments or evaluations and engaging in mentoring and technical assistance learning.” (P2) (159-161)

“... are seminars and training, peer mentoring, School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) session and lecturing and teaching.” (P3) (250-251)

“I undergone seminars and workshop initiated by the Division, District and the school.” (P4) (335-336)

“The opportunity for professional development that I experienced since I started teaching are mostly in the curriculum aspects, seminars and workshops....” (P5) (424-426)

Continuing professional development accepts that people focus on continuous improvement in their professional skills and knowledge beyond the initial fundamental training needed to complete the work. In teaching, such advancement was called In-service training, or INSET, with the accentuation on conveyance instead of the result. In-service training (INSET) is a school-based course workshop concerning the necessities of teachers in further developing their teaching methods, classroom management, professional development, and advancement of skills and knowledge towards the upliftment of students learning. It was intended for the labor advancement of the school system and education in general, given that teachers are to perform efficiently and effectively in their practice.

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Practical in-service training prompts advanced school learning environments that will comprise communities that will allow learning and steady improvement to the learners and teachers who work there and have a typical vision in lifelong learning. It enables the practice of effective teaching inside the classroom. It is vital viewpoints to upgrade teachers' professionalism identified with their idea to improve the quality of their work are the primary purpose of In-service Training (National Policy Board for Educational Administration, 2015; Tzivinikou, S., 2015; OECD, 2016; Osamwonyi, E. F., 2016; Usman, Y. D., 2016; Gomendio, M., 2017; Melesse, S. & Gulie, K., 2019).

Knowledge Application

The emergent theme in improving the teaching and learning process is knowledge application. Knowledge application is implored especially in preparing and delivering the lesson. Teachers often apply the learning they get from certain continuing professional development activities. It enables individuals to continue to make a significant commitment to the profession and become more successful in the work environment. Application of knowledge helps career progress and move into new positions that qualify to lead, impact, mentor, and guide others.

"In teaching during, before, and after. It also helps you in preparation of lesson, learning materials, during the assessment of learners, teaching-learning." (P1) (57-59)

"CPD knowledge be used by an individual assessment on their professional growth. With the acquired knowledge from CPD, we can assess our own skills in teaching if it is improving or still on the standards set by the old curriculum." (P2) (164-167)

"CPD knowledge can be used to improve teaching and learning process by sharing your notion to your colleagues and by making it as a part of daily practices." (P3) (255-257)

"CPD knowledge be used by individual assessment, it is done by tracking and documenting your gained knowledge and learning experiences to improve teaching and learning process." (P4) (339-341)

"I can use my CPD knowledge to improve my teaching and process knowledge through right application in my works." (P5) (433-435)

Continuing professional development can convey a more profound comprehension of being a professional, along with enthusiasm for the ramifications and impacts of work. It adds skills and knowledge to what you already have and helps you be a good teacher; you can perform competently as a teacher and meet the assumptions of your learners and superiors. These means lead to an increase in public trust in the individual and their profession.

Continuing professional development is significant because it guarantees you keep on being capable in your profession. It is progressing interaction and proceeds all through a professional's career. Thus, reliable and conveyed professional development is substantial for its transfer and expresses advantages to the individual, profession, and the public. As a result, teachers can utilize the information obtained in new situations. Individuals engaged in CPD activities should keep track of acquired knowledge and progress for reflection and application of skills (Timperley, H. S., 2015; Payne, M., 2015; OECD, 2016; Hyatt, M., 2017; Kloosterman, V., 2019; PRC Resolution No. 2019-1146, 2019; The Institute of Export and International Trade, 2019; Burton, L., 2021).

Organizational CPD

Conducting organizational continuing professional development activities is another way to ensure that the Department of Education can maximize its full utilization. It is mainly acquired and more convenient to teachers in the field. A CPD activity from the employer is an assurance that adequately maximizes. Organizations know their employees' needs very well, thus making them the better continuing professional development service providers.

"... I joined webinars, and also in the LAC session." (P1) (61-62)

"If the DepEd will require its employee to take CPD and offer free or affordable seminars and training with CPD given by the Division, Region, National, and International level." (P2) (172-174)

"I do avail CPD accredited activities through online registration and if my name is on the DepEd memo's list." (P3) (259-260)

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“Through attending seminars and training given by the Division.” (P4) (343)

“It may be by strengthening the best CPD activities they could see in the field and giving more available and more economically training or seminars with CPD to the teachers. If possible, hands-on training with assessment and evaluation after.” (P4) (346-349)

“... right for his position and task in school. It is given more importance and focus to ensure that the task and responsibility given to teachers will be accomplished.” (P5) (444-447)

Continuing professional development is a crucial segment of modern organizational strategy. By supporting the professional development of teachers, they will have a sense of fulfillment at work. By putting resources into teachers' improvement, authoritative ability and skill are additionally determined forward, and consequently, CPD should be viewed as a primary segment of organizational success. Henceforth, organizations should consistently uphold employees' continuous self-improvement and equal learning opportunities. Thus, CPD is also the responsibility of the organization. Well planned program, interactive with an evaluation component, will avoid pitfalls and the same time, encourage the participants (Ramasamy, D. & Gilbert, S. S., 2017; Bretl, C., 2020; Turner, I., 2020).

The current continuing professional development model inside the association comprises staff undertaking CPD activities during a compulsory training day. It enhances with improvement activities, sport, and holistic treatment. During this period, teachers needed to spend days inside the industry, known as industrial upskilling, seeing new activities and working practices to update knowledge. Significantly, guaranteeing that the knowledge transferred to learners is current. Developing teachers' knowledge about the subject is a core element of continuing professional development. Therefore, professional development in the workplace might be coordinated as organized activity or courses fully intended to upgrade professional expertise, keep a group of professionals up-to-date, or support change in the organization (Bartleton, L., 2018; Dlamini, R. & Mabatha, K., 2018; Burton, L., 2021).

Table 2: Main Theme: Perceived Challenges on Continuing Professional Development

Cluster Themes	Emergent Themes
I. Challenges in availing CPD activities 32. Financial availability 33. Time 34. Difficulty in earning CPD points 35. Limited opportunities	9. Encountered Challenges

Encountered Challenges

The teaching workforce is the most crucial resource in the department to achieve its mission and vision in implementing education. Thus, further enhancement of professionals through the continuing professional development activities was encouraged. The participants encountered several barriers in taking up CPD learning activities identified in this study. These were the financial constraints, time, limited opportunity, and the availability of CPD. The researcher anticipates that would alleviate the barriers and allow active engagement of teachers in continuing professional development through these.

“Financial; Availability of slots in CPD because some of the CPD activities has limited slots and was easily filled in; and the time.” (P1) (35-37)

“The challenges encountered by the teacher in complying CPD activities are the money and time. I can handle it through shouldering the expenses.” (P3) (236-238)

“The challenges that the teachers faced in complying CPD activities are the time management, and financial needs.” (P5) (410-412)

“Difficulty in earning points or certificates with CPD credited because not all teachers were given a chance to take CPD activities, like International, National or Regional seminars. It will depend on teacher’s financial and availability.” (P2) (140-143)

‘Difficulty in earning points or certificates with CPD credited because not all are given a chance to take CPD activities outside the department.’ (P4) (321-323)

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Quality education is the focus of most educational systems. It is the very reason teachers should be professionally developed because they influence learners' quality performance and achievement. Therefore, teachers should prioritize professional development in the education system to create and enhance teachers' knowledge and skills; many reports could infer that the strength of companies, organizations, and countries depends on the workers' intellectual qualities. Professional development is essential in uplifting human resources by efficiently and effectively meeting the organization's needs through globalization trends. The successful implementation of professional development includes cooperation, time, long-term commitment, and resources (Maria, M. & Garcia, I., 2016; Gomendio, M., 2017; Livingston, K., 2017).

In many educational systems, teachers are seldom given continuing professional development opportunities. Lack of time and the oppressive workload are the most common challenges connected to faculty development. Lack of an appropriate course to facilitate learning the necessary skills, insights, innovation, and value can deteriorate. Many believe that the degree of interest in participation in professional development activities is an element of such support that teachers will partake in or the challenges they experience (Kaspina, R., 2015; Mahmoudia, F. & Özkana, Y., 2015; Bernadine, G. G. K., 2019).

Table 3: Main Theme: Impact of Continuing Professional Development

Cluster Themes	Emergent Themes
J. New acquired knowledge 36. Learned so many 37. Acquired learning 38. Reliable 39. Additional knowledge	10. Additional Learning
K. Current work practice 40. Enhance knowledge in lesson delivery 41. Technical assistance 42. Expertise and effectiveness 43. Accomplish task	11. Task Fulfillment
L. Help with work 44. Planning and delivery of lesson 45. Conscious in lesson preparation 46. Aware of what to do 47. Make task easier 48. Strategies and techniques	12. Curriculum Implementation
M. On the learners 49. Able to participate in lesson discussion 50. Understanding and ease in learning 51. Impact on learners	13. Engage Learners
N. On the school 52. Contribute 53. Gain high performance 54. Shown achievement 55. Competitive learners 56. Accomplish tasks on time	14. School Achievement
O. On the community 57. Learners practice what is taught to them 58. Competitive individuals	15. Student Applied Learning
P. Evidence collected 59. Students grade 60. Students output	16. Students Performance
Q. Curriculum Implementation 61. Enhance skills and method 62. Equipped teachers need 63. Capacitated with the requirements 64. Guide and knowledge in curriculum Implementation	17. Teachers Competence
R. The mechanism used in the evaluation 65. Teachers profile 66. Survey forms, evaluation, and interview 67. Learners grade 68. Teachers portfolio	18. Teachers Assessment
S. Implemented in practice 69. Teaching strategy 70. Mastery of the lesson and classroom management 71. The mechanism used in teaching	19. Curriculum Instruction

The public secondary school teachers' perception revealed an Impact of Continuing Professional Development. Teachers teach the knowledge and skills they have to their learners, and at the same time, the learners take it to practice. Thus, it results in a progressive community due to the composition of competitive individuals.

Additional Learning

Additional learning heightens up the previous knowledge in terms of CPD. Teachers can reflect their prior knowledge to the new understanding they have acquired. They can make it as a basis to further improve their selves. Teachers ensure that they can use the acquired knowledge in the teaching-learning process.

“It compliments because I just earn units and I have learned so many while taking up my master’s degree like branches of science.” (P1) (68-69)

“Newly acquired knowledge will help us assess if the knowledge we have already known are still effective and efficient to use these days.” (P2) (177-178)

“Since we are following a spiral curriculum, so that makes a new acquired learning relatable to already known knowledge.” (P3) (268-269)

“I can say that it compliment based on the webinars and school-based initiated activities. The newly acquired knowledge will help us be effective and efficient during these days.” (P4) (352-354)

“I think, I have gained additional knowledge and have widened or deepen my skills on delivering the lessons properly, and be able to accomplish the requirements that were given to me as a teacher.” (P5) (450-453)

Teachers constantly seek professional growth by attending seminars, workshops, conferences, research for advanced studies, among others. Engage in serious reflection to define ways of developing practice skills. They are self-directed, independent, lifelong learner-professionals who continuously strive for professional growth. By doing this, they enhance their expertise in encompassing their teaching roles, responsibilities, and obligations among their stakeholders. Thus, CPD gives new knowledge in dealing with first-hand or complex situations, focusing on learning and development to achieve career goals, provides confidence, and proves your commitment to enhancing skills and knowledge. It enables them to prepare, develop, and maintain proficiency in their practice. CPD should make individuals eager to learn more information, master new skills, and create opportunities to expand on what they already know (Payne, M., 2015; Care Council for Wales, 2016; Bartleton, L., 2018; Sahagun, J. A. P. & Matriano, E. A., 2019).

Task Fulfillment

Task fulfillment is the emergent theme that arises in the impact of current CPD practice. Teachers were aware that they needed to learn to teach well and accomplish the required task. They considered CPD activities to be the answer for their continuous search in learning.

“Well, it develops my confidence. It increases my knowledge of strategies, especially during experiments and the activities of the students. I know now how to handle them. There are many strategies taught to motivate students to participate during activities.” (P1) (74-78)

“CPD gives a huge and clear impact to my current practices through self-assessment and eagerness to take in technical assistance for improvement.” (P2) (180-182)

“Through expertise and effectiveness as a teacher is already a proof that CPD gives impact on your current practice.” (P3) (271-272)

“CPD impacts my current practice on delivering the lesson, especially during this time of the pandemic.” (P4) (356-357)

“I am able to accomplish my present task appropriately and I am able to enjoy because I understand the responsibility of being a teacher.” (P5) (455-458)

As the breadth and profundity of teaching and the scope of education are confronted with changing fast, requests for elevated expectations, and calls for working on quality, teachers currently need to refresh and work on their abilities through in-service training, participation in external courses, and the cycle of reflective practice. It involves developing skills, knowledge, and personal qualities to accomplish professional duties and responsibilities. Hence, CPD sometimes alludes to a learning structure and professional development activities that add to continuous professional effectiveness

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and competence. CPD assists individuals withholding a steady arrangement of high-quality, applicable skills and knowledge throughout their professional life (Care Council for Wales, 2016; Bartleton, L., 2018; Burton, L., 2021).

Curriculum Implementation

Preparation and delivery of lesson is the current work practice applied by the participants. Teachers can teach well due to the continuing professional development activities that they acquired. They believed that the acquired knowledge equips them in the teaching field. Ensure that curriculum implementation is not jeopardized.

"I can use it in planning my lessons, preparation, and delivery of lessons." (P1) (84-85)

"It makes me more conscious of what and how to prepare my lessons." (P2) (184-185)

"It makes me more aware on what I have to do. It boosts my self-confidence in work by having more knowledge." (P3) (359-360)

"It helps me through new learning, strategies, techniques, skills, innovations, and much more opportunities." (P5) (460-462)

Changes in the educational system and worldwide requirements request staff improvement activities. Furthermore, teachers' quality is the most elevated determinant of acknowledging quality in education. It infers that further developing teachers' ability is a central point of interest in guaranteeing quality education. It assumes a critical part in teaching, mainly because perceived that the quality of our education system relies upon the overall quality of teachers (Usman, Y. D., 2016; Bartleton, L., 2018; Melesse, S. & Gulie, K., 2019).

Professional development intended to work with change should be explicitly taught and centered around the classroom level's everyday activities. Teachers need it because initial teacher education cannot contain all the required information in the profession. Thus, teachers need to develop expertly with the goal that they do their obligations adequately and productively. Additionally, CPD embraces various approaches and teaching and learning styles in different settings. It is distinct from the broader concept of learning. It is mainly associated with people's professional identities and roles and the organization's goals they are working for (Macheng, P., 2016; Sharick, S., 2016; Tran, S. K., 2017; Dlamini, R. & Mbatha, K., 2018).

Engage Learners

Continuing professional development activities applied by teachers engage the learners during the delivery of the lesson. Teachers can use different techniques and strategy in teaching that engages learners. Engaging learners in learning increases their attention and focus, challenges them to practice and develop higher-order thinking skills, and advances significant learning experiences.

"In some way, I am able to apply and you can see the results are okay due to learners' participation." (P1) (88-90)

"... it also gives a clear understanding and ease in learning their lessons." (P2) (190-191)

"Yes, because if we are updated of the current trends in education we are more capable of teaching our learners. We can be sure that they gain knowledge and skills through our teaching." (P4) (363-365)

"It does have impact on the learners, specifically in comprehension of the assignments that I gave, and the new knowledge that I was able to partake." (P5) (465-467)

CPD must be supported to promote a professional learning environment that supports enriched learning for teachers and students. It is characterized as practical professional development activities that assist teachers in securing information regarding new perspectives about learning and how individuals comprehend, expanding their subject matter. Thus, building up a sound base of knowledge show learners in more impressive and significant manners—in this way, proposing that what is of significance important are teachers—procuring knowledge on approaches to engage learners in learning to improve results ultimately. Through expressing the means of CPD, teachers become furnished with explicit development opportunities that empower self-improvement, upgrade their professionalism and augment their qualities with the comend result of improving the quality of teacher learning and maximizing learners' achievement (Usman, Y. D., 2016; Gomendio, M., 2017; Bartleton, L., 2018).

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Professional development in the time of accountability requires a crucial change in teacher training that prompts expansions in students learning in the classroom. The standards have been reworked with a more grounded, clearer accentuation on students and learning, illustrating foundational principles of leadership to assist with guaranteeing that every learner is accomplished and ready for the 21st century. For figuring out how to occur, educational leaders should seek all domains of their work with unwavering attention to students for learning to happen. There has been a significant venture of exertion the world over in CPD to assist with propelling educator quality and meeting the changing necessities of learners. Therefore, CPD places students in a favorable situation to showcase new knowledge, work to excellent standards, and progress in their careers (Farrell, T. S. & Ives, J., 2015; National Policy Board for Educational Administration, 2015; Macheng, P., 2016; Wolfenden, F., 2017; Baral, D. P., 2021; Burton, L., 2021).

School Achievement

School achievement is one of the indicators of a successful implementation of continuing professional development. Participants understood that they were the primary contributors to this success. Teachers can impart the acquired knowledge to their colleagues, learners, and the community and thus lead to more outstanding school achievements.

"I can contribute even a little. There is an improvement in students, so it does have an impact in school." (P1) (96-97)

"Yes, the school can gain a high-performance rating when its teachers were capacitated and globally competent." (P2) (194-195)

"It's evidently shown on the school achievements." (P3) (282)

"Yes, because the school can produce competitive learners through their capacitated teachers." (P4) (368-369)

"It does have impact on school because I am able to accomplish additional task and made it on time. Everything is right and all the teachers have equal opportunities to improve practice and everyone partakes to develop and be excellent in their respective task." (P5) (470-475)

Teachers are needed to foster their professional competence following the requirements of their schools. Undoubtedly, professional development is a legal obligation of each educator; in this manner, the teacher may not decline to be interested in professional development activities related to his profession. Hence, the most profitable conditions for informal working environment learning is a teacher and school culture that energizes and values collaborative learning. Teacher development regularly includes sharing thoughts and encounters and cooperating to find answers for common issues experienced. These collective gatherings are additionally alluded to as 'communities of practice,' groups of individuals who share a concern or passion for something they do and figure out how to do this better as they associate and team up consistently with one another (Campbell, M. P. & Elliot, R., 2015; Qi, G. Y. & Wang, Y., 2017; Bartleton, L., 2018; Doe, J., 2021).

Professional development comprises all learning encounters and those cognizant and arranged exercises planned to be of immediate or backhanded advantage to the individual, group, or school, contributing to the quality of training in the classroom. Fostering your employees and keeping them propelled guarantees that particular skills required for organizational needs are met. CPD enables schools to develop and apply curriculum and teaching strategies (Earl, K. & Ussher, B., 2015; Belay, S., 2016; Binmohsen, S. A. & Abrahams, I., 2020).

Student Applied Learning

Learners can apply their learning to the community if the emergent theme arises. Learners gained knowledge in school and used it in the community. It empowers the individual in the community to be productive and globally competitive.

"Yes, because learners are part of the community. Learners apply their gained knowledge and skills in the community, so it does have impact. You will be able to evaluate if the learners have learned in school." (P1) (100-103)

"Yes, because the globally competitive individuals will lead to a globally competitive community." (P2) (198-199)

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“Maybe CPD will have an impact on the community as a whole if what is taught is the practice by many and it’s already part of their system.” (P3) (285-286)

“Yes, because competitive learners will apply and practice what they know in school and can lead to a productive community.” (P4) (372-373)

“Yes, it does have impact on the community based on my observation because I was able to see it in their cooperation, especially in the school works that they were able to apply.” (P5) (478-480)

CPD is student-driven and custom-made to the individual learner's need; it incorporates ideas, such as self-directed learning and practice-based learning, and encourages identifying problems and applying solutions. It affects learners' accomplishments by making challenging yet caring and supportive conditions helpful for their education. They painstakingly create and support teachers, make favorable working conditions, allocate resources, build appropriate organizational policies and systems, and participate in other profound and significant work outside the classroom. That intensely affects what occurs inside it (National Policy Board for Educational Administration, 2015; Payne, M., 2015; Regmi, K. & Jones, L., 2020).

The education system must be fruitful to create future-prepared students who can continue learning after graduating, take on their future lifework, and flourish/thrive later on in society and the environment. Thus, teachers are responsible for establishing a climate and implementing promising practices for fostering habits essential for future-prepared results. The learning needs of learners from this field of education are of most extreme significance for preparing future capable professionals by designing the initial phase in learning outcomes, which may furnish students with critical and objective thinking and analytical abilities to settle interdisciplinary and complex issues. In addition, the curriculum courses tending to professionals incorporate both content and skills, which imply that course design ought to create to support knowledge transmission and skills acquisition (Engelbrecht, W. & Ankiewicz, P., 2016; Elena, F., 2017; Wong, C. P. & Ng, D., 2020).

Students Performance

Continuing professional development activities are evidence augmented in the students' performance. Teachers teach effectively and accordingly, resulting in knowledgeable and skilled learners. As they say, learners' performance reflects a teacher's performance.

“The students’ grade, participation in written, performance, and during the summative exam.” (P1) (106-107)

“...are portfolios, Action Research, learners materials and reports.” (P3) (289-290)

“The evidence that the school and the teachers have are the written works and their performance rating.” (P4) (376-377)

“... learners based on the survey that I conducted to know what to do, making it right and do better in school task....” (P5) (486-488)

Professional development should give an effective strategy for school improvement, enhancing teachers' quality, and improving student learning. Thus, professional development is high-quality continuous training programs with concentrated products and hands-on help. Professional development essentially connects to learners' achievement. Following systematized CPD leads to positive changes in teachers' practice that improves institutional and student achievement. Thus, standards reflect a positive way to deal with leadership that emphasizes improvement and strength, is optimistic, and centers on human potential (National Policy Board for Educational Administration, 2015; Badri, M., 2016; Witte, T. & Jansen, E., 2016; Bartleton, L., 2018).

Teachers Competence

Through continuing professional development activities, teachers are being efficient and effective. Their professional skills are enhanced, making them equipped with the skills and knowledge. Their competence affects curriculum implementation.

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“The professional skills and methods are enhanced.” (P1) (109)

“As the curriculum of the Philippines changed into a better curriculum, it also requires a high level of teaching and support staff to fulfill its mission and vision to both public and private institutions. With the use of CPD, it helps all professionals to be ready as they merged with the new high trends and demands of the curriculum being implemented.” (P2) (205-210)

“CPD policy affects the curriculum implementation through equipping the teachers what they need to have so that they can teach well.” (P3) (292-293)

“As the department of education adopts a more comprehensive curriculum, it is likewise requires a significant degree of teaching and learning process to satisfy its goal. Utilization of CPD for teachers ensures the preparedness and being capacitated with the necessary requirements.” (P4) (379-383)

“CPD policy affects the curriculum implementation through appropriate guides in knowledge and teaching.” (P5) (492-494)

Trends in education changed significantly during the most recent few decades. The assumptions of teachers and students have been changing as time passes by. Therefore, teachers are forced and expected to develop their teaching skills to cope with the fast-changing literary standards. The current time of innovation requests high professional skills of services from teachers to satisfy learners, parents, and the school. Thus, it required teachers to develop professionally to cope with the vulnerable and complex situation from increasing pressure to be efficient and highly trained individuals who will teach children (Draz, M. U. & Ahmad, F., 2017; Sahagun, J. A. P. & Matriano, E. A., 2019; Porter, B. D. & Freeman, M. K., 2020).

Teachers' professional development plays a huge part in changing teaching strategies and helps them move past comprehension of the surface features of a new idea or action to a deeper understanding of a topic. Teacher professional development should hence be regarded as a continuous process. Thus, quality learners come from quality teachers. On the contrary, teachers' efficacy has powerful effects on students learning and classroom behavior. Therefore, training needs analysis and its connection to research and development were fundamental to guarantee that students get the most significant advantage and teachers have suitable training for the advancement of human capital and the country. CPD embraces various approaches and teaching and learning styles in different settings. It is distinct from the broader concept of learning, and it is mainly associated with people's professional identities, roles, and the organization's goals that they are working for (Tzivinikou, S., 2015; Timperley, H. S., 2015; Blazar, D., 2016; Sharick, S., 2016; Department of Education and Training, 2017; Gilakjani, A. P., & Sabouri, N. B., 2017; Baral, D. P., 2021).

Teachers Assessment

Teachers' assessment is the mechanism used in continuing professional development evaluation. Teachers are assessed based on their accomplishments. It makes the teacher more sensible and reflective of their work and profession.

“The teachers profiling.” (P1) (112)

“The mechanisms I did use to evaluate the CPD's effectiveness is through the survey in the form of interviews or evaluation checklist.” (P3) (296-297)

“The learner's grade is what I used to evaluate the CPD effectiveness.” (P4) (386-387)

“The mechanism that I used in evaluating effective CPD is the Teacher's Portfolio because we are able to evaluate the level of our capacity, and most of all it suits the progress and practice of teachers.” (P5) (497-501)

The Professional Standards for Teachers and Trainers in Education and Training perceive the longing for further education experts to maintain and update knowledge through research, reflection, and taking part in CPD to build up their practice. For that reason, CPD is seen as professional growth that a teacher accomplishes because of acquiring more experienced and assessing his teaching systematically. For case in point, in 2001, the Further Education Teachers Qualifications Regulations on England required that all new teachers shall hold a teaching qualification. It moved towards teachers' professional development and was reinforced in 2004 when it was declared that few educators could achieve the

designation Qualified Teacher Learning and Skills (QTLS) coordinating with Qualified Teacher Status in school. To accomplish this professional development, teachers must create a portfolio of evidence that recognizes the CPD activities they have undertaken and empower them to demonstrate the application and professional guidelines expected as an educator (Lahiff, A., 2015; Thomson, A., 2017; Melesse, S. & Gulie, K., 2019).

It is through the continuing professional development as a process of tracking and documenting the skills, knowledge, and experience that you gain formally and informally as you work, beyond any initial training. It's a record of experience, learn and afterward apply. Research has demonstrated that professional development is best for long-term, collaborative, and school-based. It should focus on students' learning, be connected to teachers' daily practices, and be associated with teachers' prior knowledge of the curriculum content and guidelines. Thus, changing the expert improvement program to participants' variety of techniques and convictions expands its effectiveness (Allen, M., 2017; Bridge, 2017; Bernadine, G. G. K., 2019).

Curriculum Instruction

Curriculum instruction is the arising emergent theme that is implemented in practice due to professional development. Teachers applied the different teaching strategies and techniques they acquired in obtaining CPD activities. Accordingly, teachers need to develop more knowledge and skills to teach efficiently and effectively.

"Improvement of Teaching-learning process: in planning, delivery, and the preparation." (P1) (115-116)

"Mastery of the lesson and classroom management by putting into consideration my diverse learners." (P2) (216-217)

"I implemented the teaching strategies that I learned to be able to teach effectively." (P3) (300-301)

"The teaching process and the classroom management because of dealing with such different kinds of learners." (P4) (390-391)

"I implemented the strategies and mechanisms used in teaching as a result of my professional progress." (P5) (504-505)

Focused on participation in professional development affects the teachers' capacity to gain and enhance knowledge and skills. They noticed the significance of emotional intelligence skills vital for good thinking, planning, and dealing with students and colleagues. Professional development has a positive effect on the teachers' ability to decide on and execute esteemed changes in teaching. The impact of professional development on authority conducts so that teachers could instruct their students effectively, along these lines accomplishing desirable balance between individual, school, and national need (Badri, M., 2016; Mestry, R., 2017; Bartleton, L., 2018).

CPD's strength is that it considers teachers to be professionals taking responsibility for their learning and improvement, practicing their professional independence empowering them to accept change and better meet the needs of the learners they teach. Therefore, professional development was recognized to be centrally significant in upholding and improving the quality of teaching and learning in schools. This diversity requires the organization of uniquely constructed CPD courses. It also demands teachers to consistently update their knowledge and skills because of the presentation of the new educational program, changes in innovation, changes in adapting needs of the learners, or potentially in the light of recent research on education and learning. In such a manner, many teachers continue to have developmental needs in curriculum and instruction (Michael, M. & Watson, C., 2015; Macheng, P., 2016; Melesse, S. & Gulie, K., 2019).

The study sought teachers to explore the experiences and understand professional growth, particularly their views, feelings, and impacts on teaching. Consequently, this study gathered the essential information required from the participants during the in-depth interview. The result of this study may equip the administrators and teachers with standards and rules in reinforcing the importance of CPD in the Division of Sarangani. The experts in the Department of Education could utilize this as a springboard in leading various training, workshops and expanding the teachers' advantages to improve their teaching performance. Consequently, it expects to impact students' learning performance positively.

Major Findings

This exploratory qualitative single case study described the perceptions of public secondary school teacher on continuing professional development in East District of Malungon, Division of Sarangani could be categorized into three main themes: The Needs for Continuing Professional Development, Perceived Challenges on Continuing Professional Development, and the Impact of Continuing Professional Development.

Teachers felt the need to upgrade and constantly sought continuing professional development activities besides the fact that it is the main requirement for license renewal. They were able to assess their skills and knowledge independently or through their portfolios. Teaching strategy and methods were the most common CPD activities teachers aim to have that empower them to do well in their teaching career. Challenges such as financial matter, time, and CPD availability usually hinder the teacher in taking up CPD activities. Still, they could compensate for these barriers through self-discipline and being resourceful.

Organizational continuing professional development activities are the primary source for teachers to improve their skills and knowledge. Teachers believe that CPD activities are better if it comes inside the department. They know the training and seminars needed, and it is more convenient and less expensive for teachers. The department can ensure the maximum utilization of the CPD activities conducted.

The Case of P1

Continuous Learning

Participant 1 perception of continuing professional development is continuous learning that enables teachers to do well in their job. Professional development helps teachers in lesson preparation and delivery. Teachers should continue to develop professionally to benefit by having the confidence she needs and partake of the learning she acquired with their colleagues, learners, school, and the community. Teachers equipped with the necessary skills in the teaching-learning process enable students to learn and apply what they learn in the community. Continuing professional development activities within the department and taking up a graduate degree was her way in obtaining continuous learning.

The Case of P2

Professional Management

Professionally managing one's learning and growth that expands knowledge and skills required in teaching is the perception of Participant 2 in terms of continuing professional development. Individual assessment of the skills and knowledge acquired is necessary to know if the education standards are met. She believes that developing and capacitating teachers with the skills needed could upgrade the teaching profession in the country. The organization should offer CPD activities with technical assistance. Teachers that are capacitated produce learners globally competitive.

The Case of P3

Professional Skills Development

Participant 3 believes that she can learn new skills and knowledge to help her endeavor by engaging in professional activities. Professional growth means developing the necessary skills and expertise that enable teachers capable of promotion. CPD activities ensure that it could be fully utilized through its quality and good product. Knowledge gained in CPD activities could improve the teaching and learning process by sharing notions with colleagues and making it a habit. It could make the difficult task easier to handle. Equipping teachers with their needs affect curriculum implementation, enabling them to teach well. Most of the CPD activities she has undertaken come from the school, district, and Division.

The Case of P4

Planned and Ongoing Developmental Process

Continuing professional development is an ongoing, planned, and developmental process, according to Participant 4. Upgrading the CPD of teachers enables them to meet higher standards and attain professional skills. CPD activities ensure teachers' preparedness as the Department of Education adopts a more comprehensive curriculum. It makes teachers more conscious and active in their professional development. It boosts his confidence in teaching by possessing the required

knowledge through continuing professional development activities that the Department offers. A productive community involves competitive learners who apply and practice what they learn in school.

The Case of P5

Continuous Training

Participant 5 believed that it is continuous training which he could impart to learners the knowledge acquired. Developing teaching strategies and applying technology in the teaching and learning process motivates him to take continuing professional development activities to cope with the continuous innovation of the education curriculum. He often joined continuing professional development activities through school sponsorship. CPD must be strengthened to appropriate teachers' needs in accomplishing the expected task. It makes him aware of and understands his roles and responsibilities as a teacher.

Comparison of Findings with Existing Studies

Continuing professional development assists individuals with holding a steady arrangement of high quality, essential skills, and knowledge all through their professional life. The significance of professional development to teachers should enhance the quality of teaching and learning. CPD places learners in a favorable position to demonstrate new knowledge, impressive standards of work, and progress in their profession.

The challenges in education are ascending with assumptions from policymakers about how teachers can do to meet those constantly increasing demands. The solution to address this gap is through continuing professional development for teachers, but unfortunately, most approaches affect teachers' capacity to satisfy these needs. It brought about changes and improved results for learners. Includes more extensive educational context, the professional learning setting, the content of the professional learning opportunities, the activities constructed to promote learning of the content, the professional learning processes enabled, the responses of diverse teacher learners, and the effect on different students, including social, personal, and academic outcomes (Timperley, H. S., 2015; Alberta Teachers' Association, 2016; Hyatt, M., 2017).

CPD views as upgrading teachers' subject knowledge and improving their training inside the classroom. Nonetheless, assuming students learning is to be improved, more effective professional learning activities should receive, resulting in positive change for teachers and learners. The traditional CPD approach described teachers as a technician. In this way, implying that teachers offered guidelines to follow, and the learner projected into the part of a passive receiver, there is little arrangement inside the school setting for reflective practice. Thus, teachers should move away from technical strategies of CPD towards more practical methods and utilize critical reflection of their own experiences, where their progress moves from descriptive inside the technological paradigm towards a more dialogic or fundamental form of thought. In addition, reflective practice helps teachers make sense of their training by expanding their perspectives and assisting them with tending to difficulties they face. It assumes a huge part in advancing self-awareness and provides the teacher with greater comprehension. The most gainful conditions for informal workplace learning are the teacher and school culture that energizes and values collaborative learning—along these lines, recommending that the way of life inside a setting can engage teachers to speak freely about their teaching and learning approaches. In this way, ready to share good practice, adding to collaborative learning, which researches shown as an effective type of CPD. Teacher development frequently includes sharing ideas and experiences, cooperating to discover answers for problems (Campbell, M. P. & Elliot, R., 2015; McGarr, O. & McCormack, O., 2015; Payne, M., 2015; Blazar, D., 2016; Karaarslanab, G. & Teksöz, G., 2016; Hyatt, M., 2017; Bartleton, L., 2018).

One resonating advantage of CPD is the chance to engage and empower individuals. It is a cycle whereby dreams and aspirations can acknowledge, and individuals can move towards their future goals. Therefore, CPD should make people eager to learn more and master new skills and opportunities to create what they already know. Notwithstanding, this could be seen as a reasonably optimistic perspective on CPD for all professions. Good professional development is recognized as containing key ingredients that incorporate a reasonable and concurred vision, considering participants' previous knowledge and advancing continuous inquiry and critical thinking. Also, it ought to include opportunities for teachers to develop understanding, expand their teaching strategies, stay updated with advances in new and arising innovation. Assume any of these critical components were missing; CPD reduction programs' effect on high-quality professional development could influence teachers' abilities and attitudes in the classroom.

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It was further improving the quality of the learners' education. It was evident that there's a need and a place for teachers' CPD, specifically for the development and improvement of schools. Most teachers would recognize the requirement for keeping preparing for new technologies, classroom practice, and educational policy assessment and updates. Thus, effective and quality teacher enhancement could influence teachers' abilities and attitudes inside the classroom, which was undoubtedly a primary advantage to an additional increasing in learners' training (Lahiff, A., 2015; Timperley, H. S., 2015; Bartleton, L., 2018).

In this way, they propose that what was of vital significance was teachers securing knowledge on approaches to engage learners in learning to improve outcomes ultimately. In this manner, teachers become equipped with explicit advancement opportunities that empower personal growth, enhance their professionalism and maximize their qualities with the critical consequences of improving the quality of teacher learning and maximizing learners' achievement. It refers to that the proof was confident that good CPD results in teachers' performance improved and, subsequently, expecting increasing student achievement (Campbell, M. P. & Elliot, R., 2015; Timperley, H. S., 2015; Bartleton, L., 2018).

Proposed Intervention Program

Continuing professional development can be referred to as continuous learning. The CPD program aims to improve individuals professionally by keeping them updated and continuously improving in their professions. Teachers can acquire CPD formally when obtaining a graduate degree program or informally like reading.

Based on the findings, public secondary school teachers know the importance of continuing professional development; they recognized that it would be favorable to have organizational continuing professional development activities. Conducting school-based in-service training is more convenient, less expensive, and more appropriate to address their needs.

I. IDENTIFYING INFORMATION**PROJECT TITLE:**

“CPD Pasiglahin, sa Paaralan Pagtibayin”

PROPONENT:

Eugie Mae R. Fernandez

PARTICIPANTS/BENEFICIARIES:

Public Secondary School Teachers, School Administration, Learners, External Stakeholders, and External CPD Providers

PROJECT COST:

Php 30,000.00

SOURCE OF FUND:

School Monthly Operating and Other Expenses (MOOE), other school and personal funds

DURATION:

1 year

II. PROGRAM DESCRIPTION

This intervention program is known as “CPD Pasiglahin, sa Paaralan Pagtibayin”. It addresses the gap in obtaining and strengthening the continuing professional development activities in the school context.

III. RATIONALE

Professional development in the more extensive sense alludes to the advancement of an individual in their professional career. Specifically, teacher professional development is achieved through acquiring experiences and systematically assessing their skills. Professional development is a systematic intervention that can be used for teachers' development.

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Rapid changes in the educational system require dynamism. In response to these changes, teachers need to regularly upgrade and update their knowledge and skills to cope: teachers' experiences, processes, and the context where Continuing Professional Development assesses. Continuous school-based in-service training is a great way to update the skills and knowledge of teachers. Additionally, school-based in-service training will be cost-effective, practical, and easier to address the immediate concerns of teachers (Melesse, S. & Gulie, K., 2019).

IV. PROGRAM OBJECTIVE

The "CPD Pasiglahin, a Paaralan Pagtibayin" Intervention program is anchored on the CPD Framework concepts that engage in professional learning. Teachers model effective learning, recognize their own learning needs, and analyze, assess and extend their professional knowledge both collegially and independently (Queensland College of Teachers, 2017). The following are the objectives of this proposed intervention program: one, to reflect Teachers' current practice, two, to develop Professional Skills and Knowledge, three, to strengthen the Continuing Professional Development activities in the school context, and four to capacitate teachers to be globally competitive.

V. PROGRAM PLAN

Below is the matrix to carry out its plan of activities.

Key Result Area	Objectives/ Targets	Strategies/ Activities	Time Frame	Person Involved	Expected Outcome
Professional Reflection	Identify Professional Learning Needs	Assessment through checklist, journals, and record of department heads	One week	Teacher Department Head, Human Resource In-charge, Principal	Aware of their Continuing Professional Development Needs
Learning Forward	Plan Professional Learning Needs	Create Professional Development Plan	One week	Teacher, Department Head, Human Resource In-charge, Principal	School identify Developmental Needs of their Teacher
Continuing Professional Development	Engage in Professional Learning through School Context	In-service Training, Learning Action Cell, Job shadowing, Peer Mentoring, Seminar, and Workshop	Whole Year	Teacher Department Head, Human Resource In-charge, Principal, Key Resource Speakers, and External CPD Providers	Enhance Professional Skills and Knowledge
Curriculum and Planning	Apply Professional Learning	Programs, Activities, Lesson Preparation and Delivery, Classroom Management, and community involvement	Whole Year	Teacher, Leamers, Stakeholders, and School Administration	Application of the CPD learning acquired
Assessment and Reporting	Evaluate Teachers Progress	Performance Evaluation through the interview, checklist, portfolios, monitoring, and learners' output	One month	Teacher, Leamers, Stakeholders, and School Administration	Track and Record CPD Progress

VI. IMPACT OF THE PROPOSED INTERVENTION PROGRAM

1. Gain a deeper understanding of the teaching-learning theory.
2. Teachers improved knowledge in the subject area, teaching methodologies, strategies, and techniques.
3. Teachers increased opportunities for professional development with accompanying benefits.
4. Teachers get opportunities for career transition in teaching.
5. Produce globally competitive learners.

Concluding Remarks

Participants recognize the importance of CPD towards the implementation of the education curriculum. It enables them to cope up with the fast-changing trends in education. Teachers need to continue to learn, and they recognize the CPD activities that are initiated by the department are more convenient and more effective to address their needs in the teaching profession. Organizational CPD in the school context is seen as the answer to fully utilize professional development activities that will uplift the teachers' competence, and has an impact on raising standards of students that enables them to be globally competitive.

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